

Efficient Clustering Scheme in Cognitive Radio Wireless Sensor Network

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Candidate's Declaration

I hereby state that the work that is accessible in this dissertation, entitled as “**Efficient Clustering Scheme in Cognitive Radio Wireless Sensor Network**” in partial necessities of the requirements for the honor of the Degree of **Master of Technology** and submitted in CSE Department of NIT Hamirpur is my own legitimate record work carried out during a period from July 2018 to May 2019 under the supervision of **Nitin Gupta**, Assistant Professor, CSE Department, NIT Hamirpur.

The issue presented in this dissertation has not been submitted by me for the award of any other degree of this or any other Institute/University.

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This is to certify that the above statement made by the candidate is true to the best of our knowledge and belief.

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ABSTRACT

Cognitive Radio (CR) is a promising answers for spectrum shortage issue. An intellectual radio system is made out of both the primary radios whose radios need not be CR-enable whereas secondary users with CR-enable radios need not to be licensed. Clustering is a productive method to diminish energy consumption. Existing clustering algorithms for wireless sensor networks (WSN) are not appropriate in cognitive radio network and existing answers for cognitive radio systems are not reasonable for sensor networks. In this dissertation, an effective and efficient clustering algorithm for CR based WSN is proposed. Further, Sleep wake strategies has been used to make strong lifetime of an CRN. Further, K-means clustering and Affinity Propagation method is combined to choose cluster head.

Simulation results show that the proposed scheme is effective and efficient for generating lesser number of clusters, in case number of nodes are increased which decreases the overhead as well as energy consumption required to form clusters.

Keyword Used : Cognitive Radio Network, Clustering, Spectrum sensing data, Primary user, Secondary user, Primary base station, License band, Channel access, Energy utilization, Channel allocation.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Cognitive radio (CR) is a new technique, encountering quick development of wireless system because of its capability to tackle considerable issues influencing present-day wireless or remote systems. The radio range, which is normally restricted, required for the remote communication systems. Range controllers generally adopt the fixed access approach (FSA) and it is used to help various administrations and remote applications in non-interfering premises. The allotted (authorized) users reserve to exploit the designated spectrum and not allow it to use by the different users, regardless of whether the authorized clients are using it. With the expansion of wireless services over the few decades, in a few countries, the large part of the accessible spectrum has completely been allocated, which leads to the shortage issue in the spectrum. To keep up the attainable improvement of the remote or wireless communication industry, a novel arrangement should be made to redesign the utilization capability of the radio spectrum.

1.1 Cognitive Radio Network

It can automatically find out the unoccupied channels in the wireless spectrum. The channels which are not in use in the wireless spectrum are known as white space or white hole. The CRN is intelligent and dynamically adapts the transmission parameter through the environment accordingly. It is having the ability to detect whether channels are unused or not and it moves into vacant channel leaving the used one without interfering other users. It is also having the capability to do the unutilized spectrum unlicensed and licensed spectrum band. Two kinds of users that may use spectrum in the CRN namely, Primary user(PU) and secondary user(SU). PU user have licensed to use the spectrum. A SU is a user who can use spectrum only when the PU is not using it. When the PU appears again then the SU has to leave that channel. Cognitive radio allows SUs to use the spectrum without harmful interference with PUs. Figure 1.1 shows

Figure 1.1: Process of Cognitive radio

the process of cognitive radio.

A specific sets of functions to be implemented by cognitive radio include geographic location with respect to the other radiating transmitter, recognize and authorize its user. It has to sense all the wireless devices which is in the neighbourhood and adjust both the power and modulation characteristics.

Allocated range or spectrum portions are not utilized all the time by their holders, which makes range gaps. A spectrum gap, likewise called void area or white space, is a frequency band doled out to a PU, however it isn't being utilized at a specific time and at a specific location as given in the Fig 1.2 [1]. In this manner, the radio spectrum is wastefully exploited. Along these lines, the shortage and exploitation of the spectrum management require a dire intercession to upgrade the radio spectrum get to and accomplish high network execution.

Figure 1.2: Spectrum Holes

1.2 Cognitive cycle

As outlined in Figure 1.3 [2], a cognitive radio system plays out a 3-process cycle: sensing, deciding, and acting. The first process is critical since it is where the estimations are taken and the spectrum detection is performed. Due to multipath blurring, shadowing, or changing channel conditions, vulnerability influences this first process. In the perception procedure, estimations taken by the SUs are also dubious. In the next process, secondary users make a decision dependent on what has already been observed using their knowledge basis, which may have been affected by the vulnerability in the detected estimations, prompting the wrong decisions. In the last process, vulnerability spreads over the cognitive radio cycle, and some of the time the wrong actions are made. Along these lines, vulnerability proliferation impacts all the radio spectrum processes, which degrades the intellectual radio presentation. Consequently, it is important to address these vulnerability issues in the cognitive radio cycle by detecting the spectrum accurately, making the right choice, and making the correct action.

Figure 1.3: Cognitive cycle

1.3 Cognitive Radio Network Architecture

The present wireless network environment appoints the quality of being diverse of both communication technologies and spectrum policy. Therefore, it clearly states that the CR network architecture can be critical for the evolving communication procedures.

In the figure 1.5 [3] there are sections on the architecture of the CRN, it can be split into two sections, the first section can be cognitive system and the second section is primary system. The cognitive network is not having any right or license to use the desired spectrum band. However, the main system is also stated as primary system, it is accurate and licensed towards using the desired spectrum band.

In this work, in the geographical areas it has been expected that the main operators have being coexisting with the other users. There are independent bodies to control and monitor PUs and SUs. PUs are being contolled by PUBS which is a fixed base station for primary units. Similarly SUs too has a contolling body known as SUBS i.e the base station for secondary units.

The fundamental elements of the unlicensed network and primary networks are stated below:

- a) **Main user:** In the firm desired spectrum bands before the main users use it, it must be licensed. Having to accesses could be constrained depending on the base-station and must not be influenced on other individuals' activities especially those users who are not

Figure 1.4: Architecture of CRN

approved.

- b) **Primary Base-Station:** The main base station has a secure framework, it has organized sections and those sections have spectrum licensed. The main base station has not got any cognitive radio or the ability of spectrum division to those who use cognitive radio. It might be important for the main base station to have two radios, the two radios are inheritance and cognitive radio. Convention for the main system, so that the individuals who are using the cognitive radio can have accesses.
- c) **Cognitive Radio Users:** This is when the users cannot use the spectrum licensed because they have no right to use it. Therefore, the spectrum can be opened if it is used in a resourceful way. The cognitive radio users capacities include the spectrum choice, spec-

trums identifying, cognitive radio MAC/ finding the direction, transportation/ settlement and spectrum handoff. The cognitive radio user must have the abilities to connect with the base station and the cognitive radio users.

- d) **Cognitive Radio Base Station:** Cognitive radio base station is firmly based around sections with cognitive radio capabilities. Cognitive radio base station provides single hop association with cognitive radio users that do not have spectrum license. It is shown in figure 3 that cognitive radio users can do two things, the first thing they can do is to connect or contact with each other in many different ways. The second thing they can do is get accesses to the base station.
- e) **CRN Access:** Cognitive radio users can have their own cognitive radio-station official and unlicensed spectrum bands. In the CRN all the assistance happens inside, their average accesses is combined with autonomous of the primary network.
- f) **Cognitive Radio Ad Hoc Access:** Cognitive radio clients can connect with one another through ad hoc connections by being authorized and unlicensed spectrum bands. Similarly, cognitive radio clients could get their personal average accesses innovation.
- g) **Primary Network Access:** If the primary base system is permitted the cognitive radio client can get to the primary base station through the authorized band. There could be like different accesses categories, cognitive radio clients must be able to strengthen the average accesses innovation of the primary system. Furthermore, primary base station must strengthen the cognitive radio capacities.

1.4 Applications of CRN's

CRN's application is having large range of application domain. CRN node can be implemented any where in place of wireless sensor network. There are some example where CRN's node implemented like surveillance machine, intelligent roads, medical, security, object tracking, actuation, facility management, telemetries, preventive maintenance, and monitor of indoor and outdoor environment. The following are given some important areas where CRN's node can be implemented with example.

- a) **Health Care:** In health care system, for example, telemedicine, wearable body sensors are being utilized progressively. Various remote sensor nodes are put on patients and get basic information for remote observing by social insurance providers. Remote BAN-helped human services frameworks have just been practically speaking in some remote regions of creating nations, for example, in Nepal and India. Remote BAN for medicinal services frameworks is appropriate for regions, where the quantity of well being pros is generally low. Medicinal information is basic, deferral and mistake delicate. In this way, the constraint of customary WSN, as examined in the past area limits the possibility of telemedicine. The QoS may not be accomplished at an attractive dimension if the working range band is packed in helpful 'telemedicine with BAN'. The utilization of 'CR wearable body remote sensors can relieve these issues because of data transmission, sticking and worldwide operability, henceforth improve unwavering quality. A lot of research has been done in the territory of WBASN. The necessities of psychological radio execution in remote therapeutic systems are examined in reference.
- b) **Public Security and Military Application:** Conventional WSNs are utilized in numerous military and open security applications, for example, (a) concoction natural radiological and atomic assault location and examination; (b) direction control; (c) assemble the data of fight harm assessment; (d) war zone reconnaissance; (e) knowledge right hand (f) focusing on, and so on. In the combat zone or in questioned areas, a foe may send sticking sign to disturb radio correspondence channels. In such circumstances, since CR-WSs can handoff frequencies over a wide range, CR-WSNs can utilize distinctive recurrence groups, in this way maintaining a strategic distance from the recurrence band with a sticking sign. Likewise, some military applications require an enormous transfer speed, least channel access and correspondence delays . For such applications, CR-WSNs can be a superior choice.
- c) **Real-Time Surveillance Applications:** Real-time surveillance applications, for example, traffic observing, biodiversity mapping, living space checking, natural observing, ecological conditions checking that influence yields and animals, water system, submerged WSNs, vehicle following, stock following, fiasco help activities, scaffolds or passage observing, require least channel access and correspondence delay. Some ongo-

ing reconnaissance applications are exceptionally delay-touchy and require high unwavering quality. A deferral because of a connection disappointment can likewise happen in multihop WSNs if the channel condition isn't great. Then again, WS nodes bounce to another channel in the event that it locate another inactive channel with a superior condition in CR-WSNs. Channel collection and the utilization of numerous diverts simultaneously are conceivable in CR-WSNs to expand the channel transfer speed.

- d) **Diverse Purpose Sensing:** Progressively, the utilization of wireless sensors in a similar region for various targets exists together. In a regular WSN, those wireless sensors endeavor to get to the divert in non-helpful habits. With the assistance of a productive medium access control (MAC) convention, CR-WSN may choose various channels for various applications considering load adjusting and reasonableness.
- e) **Vehicular Networks and Transportation:** The IEEE 1609.4 standard proposes multi-direct activities in remote access for vehicular environment (WAVE). The WAVE framework works on the 75 MHz range in the 5.9 GHz band with one control channel and six administration channels. Every single vehicular client should fight for channel access and use it to transmit the data in the 5.9 GHz band. Be that as it may, regardless it experiences range deficiency issues. This range shortage issue and the prerequisites of subjective radio in WAVE have been examined. Some primer works in CR-empowered vehicular correspondences have just been done. Vehicular remote sensor systems are developing as another system worldview for proactively assembling observing data in urban conditions. CR-WSNs are probably going to be increasingly pertinent in this field. Despite the fact that this territory still should be analyzed, a few conventions for parkway security utilizing CR-WSNs have been proposed.
- f) **Indoor Application and Home Appliances:** Numerous potential and developing indoor applications require a thick WSNs condition to accomplish a sufficient QoS. Regular WSNs experience critical difficulties in accomplishing solid correspondence since ISM groups in indoor regions are amazingly packed. A few instances of the indoor uses of WSNs are keen structures, home observing frameworks, production line computerization, individual stimulation, and so on. CR-WSNs can alleviate the difficulties looked by traditional indoor WSNs applications.

g) **Intensive-Bandwidth Applications:** Interactive media applications, for example, on-request or live video spilling, sound, and still pictures over asset compelled WSNs, are incredibly testing a result of their gigantic data transfer capacity necessities. Other WSN applications, for example, WSNs in an emergency clinic condition, vehicular WSNs, following, reconnaissance, and so on., have tremendous spatial and fleeting varieties in information thickness related with the hub thickness. These applications are data transmission hungry, defer unfortunate and bursty in nature. Since in CR-WSN, SUs can get to different channels at whatever point accessible and vital, CR WSN is truly reasonable for these sorts of data transfer capacity hungry applications. Rehmani et al. revealed divert holding in CR-WSNs for such transmission capacity concentrated applications.

1.5 Merits of CRN's

CRN's merits or advantages is having large range of domain. Contingent upon the application, a WSN made out of sensor nodes furnished with cognitive radio [4] may profit by its potential favorable circumstances:

- a) **Opportunistic channel usage for bursty traffic:** countless sensor hubs recognizing an event produce bursty traffic and endeavor to gain the channel to send their readings. This expands the likelihood of collisions and bundle loses, which diminishes the general communications unwavering quality with excessive power utilization. Crafty access to numerous multiple channels may reduce these potential difficulties.
- b) **Adaptability for reducing power consumption:** The dynamic nature of the remote channel causes vitality utilization because of packet loses and retransmissions. cognitive radio able sensor hubs might most likely adjust to changing channel conditions, which would build transmission productivity, and thus help diminish control utilized for transmission and reception.
- c) **Dynamic spectrum access:** The current WSN deployments expect a fixed spectrum portion over very jam-packed unlicensed bands additionally utilized by different gadgets. Additionally, a spectrum lease for an authorized band intensifies the general arrangement

cost. Henceforth, to have the option to participate productively with different kinds of users, opportunistic spectrum access might be used in WSNs.

- d) **Energy detection or identification:** Implementation effortlessness and computational complexities low: a vitality sensor can be actualized like a spectrum analyzer by averaging frequency containers of an FFT. Since it is not hard to implement, the ongoing work on the detection of the essential users has commonly received the energy detector. vitality detection is the optimum identification if the essential user signal is not known.
- e) **Feature detection:** The principle merits of the component identification is that it can segregate the commotion energy from the adjusted signal vitality. Moreover, cyclostationary include identification can identify the signals with low SNR .
- f) **Cooperative detection:** Lower detection affectability prerequisites. Channel hindrances, for example, shadowing, multipath blurring, building infiltration and multipath blurring loses high affectability necessities on cognitive radios. The affectability prerequisite can be definitely diminished by cooperation detection. Improve the deftness of the detection. One of the greatest difficulties in cognitive radio is the decrease of overall detection time. Helpful detection can diminish recognition time contrasted with clumsy detection, so it can improve the dexterity of the identification.
- g) **Interference-based detection:** Interference-based recognition can keep away from the concealed terminal issue.

1.6 Demerits of CRN's

The demerits of cognitive radio network is shown in the following:

- a) **Interference-based detection:** Firstly, It's difficult to gauge interference temperature. Secondly,during the inerferced based identification, cognitive radio clients can't recognize real signal from the primary users and clamor or impedance.
- b) **Cooperation detection:** Firstly, cooperation builds the overhead of the cognitive radio system. Furthermore, cognitive radio clients are generally minimal cost and low power

gadgets that probably won't have devoted equipment for cooperation. Therefore information and cooperation data must be multiplexed that can cause degradation of throughput for the cognitive client. In conclusion, helpful identification needs control stations.

- c) **Feature detection:** Feature identification requires long perception time and higher computationally complex. Likewise, feature detection needs the earlier learning of the primary clients.
- d) **Energy detection:** The presentation of the energy detector is exceedingly helpless to commotion level vulnerability. The commotion vulnerability causes issues particularly on account of a straightforward energy detector since it is hard to set the thresholds appropriately without the information of the precise commotion level. Besides, an energy detector can't separate between tweaked signals, clamor, and obstruction. The presentation of an energy detector in shadowing and blurring environments degrades clearly. In addition, it is difficult to choose the correct threshold for energy recognition.
- e) **Matched filter detection:** It requires an earlier knowledge of each primary client, if this data isn't precise, the matched filter performs inadequately.

1.7 CRN's issues

The primary reason for the CR is to acknowledge dynamic access to the ideal spectrum so as to have correspondence. While implementation of cognitive radio as a challenging job. A commonplace cognitive radio situation comprises of SUs that coincide with the PUs. PU has a need to utilize the spectrum as it has legacy rights for the spectrum get to. SU opportunistically get to the spectrum when it found that PU isn't utilizing the spectrum or underlay access to the range, when both PU and SU coincide, with severe requirement over non-obstruction among the users. The primary issues of CR are as under.

- a) **Security Issues:** The CRN has some security issues such as Not acceptable interference to authorized users, Banning the utilization of idle channels for secondary users, Restricting the utilization of common control channel by for all intents and purposes making a bottleneck issue, Access to private information, Alteration of data, Injection of wrong data.

- b) **Sensing Techniques:** The interference of secondary users to primary users relies upon the detecting accuracy of secondary users. If secondary users can detect the channels with high precision, interference with the primary user's decreases. Contingent upon the detecting system, there is a tradeoff between the detecting delay and detecting accuracy. The system that takes a long detecting time has more accuracy with the expense of delay and vice versa.
- c) **Cooperative Sensing:** CR remote sensors may experience inaccurate decisions since radio-wave propagation through the remote channels has an antagonistic factors, for example, shadowing, multipath fading, and building penetration. CR remote sensors are hardware imperatives and can't detect different channels at the same time. In this manner, CR remote sensors participate and share their detecting data with each other to improve the detecting accuracy and performance.

1.8 Clustering in CRN

Clustering is nothing but creating the different groups, that groups contain the similar elements. Elements in that same group are similar as much as possible. Elements in the different groups are completely different from the other group's element. Clustering is often referred as unsupervised learning techniques. Example: A group of dinners sitting in a restaurant, suppose there are two tables in a restaurant t1 and t2. The group of the table sitting on a table t1 might be related to each other, it may be a group of family members, may be groups of colleagues, etc. Even the people sitting on t2 connected with each other but only when the people sitting on table t2. If it compares the people sitting on table t1 with people sitting on table t2 entirely different. All are not at all related to each other. One more example, when visited a big bazaar, wallmart or retail store, it is found that similar items are grouped together. It is not like the items are just placed anywhere or mixed with each other. So it creates a group or cluster of items to show that it can easily shop and finds the things. The same varieties of apples are placed in one place while other varieties of apples are placed other like red and green apples are placed in different placed. Clustering is used Flickr maps photos uses the cluster to reduce the number of marks on the map. Amazon uses popular the recommended system which is using the clustering to show the recommended list of products according to its past purchases

history. Netflix recommends movies based on watch history. Whatever have watched it will recommend the similar movies. So generally it can say that Clustering cab used to segment the customer, market in the marketing. Clustering is also used by social network sites in marketing new groups based on user’s data. Clustering can help the business to manage the data better.

Generally, it uses the cluster for image segmentation, grouping webpages, market segmentation, and information retrieval. Cluster are interconnected into an enormous network. A gateway node is an individual from one cluster that can achieve the individual from other clusters. The interconnection clustering is shown in Fig. 1.6 [5], it can be seen that the clusters are interconnected in two ways: the two cluster heads is associated with one node gateway or associated by two nodes gateway if there node is not available is the 1-hop node of two cluster heads. There are different kinds of user cluster: the cluster head, node gateway and node ordinary as shown in Fig 1.6.

Figure 1.5: Clustering interconnected by gateway nodes

1.8.1 Types of clustering

There are mainly three types of clustering:

- a) **Exclusive clustering:** Exclusive clustering is a hard clustering where the data related to exclusively one cluster. K-mean clustering is an example of exclusive clustering. If there are two circles, one is having blue data points and other circle having pink data points.

Figure 1.6: Inter-cluster connection

Both these clusters are entirely different from each other. It is not at all related to each other.

- b) **Overlapping clustering:** Overlapping clustering is a soft cluster where data points belong to multiple clusters. An example is fuzzy or c-mean clustering. Some of the blue data points overlap with the blue data points.
- c) **Hierarchical clustering:** hierarchical clustering depends utilizing these clustering procedures to find a hierarchy of clusters, where this chain of importance takes after a tree structure, called a dendrogram.

1.9 Introduction to K-mean clustering

K-mean clustering is an algorithm of unsupervised machine learning which is utilized to generate a normal cluster in unlabelled information. Its main goal is to groups in the data. The number of groups or clusters is represented by k. The algorithm then runs iteratively to assign each data points to one of the k groups based on the features that already provided. It is an iterative calculation that comprises of a cluster task and a centroid development step. If k is the number of clusters generated and training data(unlabelled data) then the k-Means algorithm can be characterized to produce k number of the cluster from the information. K-means algorithm

can be applied to a numeric or continuous data with a smaller number of dimensions. It can be applied to any scenario where it has to group several things from a randomly distributed collection of things. For eg, document classification where it can create the document and multiple categories based on tags, topics and contains the documents. K-means algorithm is one of the highly suitable algorithms for this purpose.

1.9.1 Working of K-mean clustering

Assume that the working of the algorithm for, $k=3$, here k in k -means is nothing but the total number of clusters required. So here the total number of cluster is three. It randomly select the three data points, these three data points are nothing but assuming that centroid of each cluster. Now measure the distance between the first point and the three clusters so that shows the distance from point 1 to the red cluster as can see in the below figure 1.8. Next, it shows the

Figure 1.7: Distance from 1st node to red cluster

distance from the first point to the blue cluster and the third figure shows the distance from the first point to the green cluster. Now assign the first point and add the first point to the nearest cluster since in this case, the nearest one is red. So the first point will be added to the red cluster. The next is to calculate the mean for the red cluster including the new point which is recently added to the cluster. The mean value lies somewhere between the two points within the red cluster as shown in the figure. Now figure out the second point or which cluster does the second point belongs to. Use the same procedure have done before but measure the distance to the red mean. Here different distance from the second point to different red, blue and green clusters. Once this have done with the measuring assign the second point to the nearest cluster which is again the red cluster. Next, calculate the mean within the red cluster. It will repeat the same procedure for other remaining points. This procedure will repeat until it get an original result as shown in the figure 1.9. Here k is very important. Each time it increase the cluster the variation decreases. The number of clusters is equal to the number of data points then, in that

Figure 1.8: An expected cluster

case, the variation is zero. As the number of clusters increases, the total variation decreases shown graph in the below figure 1.10 [6].

Figure 1.9: graph of variation Vs number of cluster

The above-given graph shows where on the x-axis is the number of clusters and reduction in a variation on the y-axis. On the graph, it can be seen that the huge reduction in variance with $k = 3$. But after that, there is no such change in variation. This point of change is called the elbow point and the value of this point is the one which decides the value of k . So in order to find out the value of k , it needs to find out the elbow from the elbow plot.

1.10 Motivation

Cognitive radios offer the guarantee of being a innovation technology that will empower the future wireless world. Cognitive radios are completely programmable remote gadgets that can detect their environment and dynamically adjust their transmission waveform, spectrum use, channel access method, and networking protocol as required for a good system and application execution. One of the main issue is that on how to do efficient Clustering in a CRN such that

consumption of power is also minimized. In this dissertation work, the main motivation of this work is to design efficient and less power consumption clustering scheme in a CRNs.

1.11 Problem Statement

Inefficient clustering in CRN may lead to high power consumption and reduction of the lifetime of nodes in the cognitive radio network. The objective of the proposed work is to design a clustering algorithm such that a lesser number of the cluster are created while the number of nodes are increased.

1.12 Dissertation Layout

The dissertation carries five chapters. The following details of each chapter are given in brief:

Chapter 2 : Literature review: The literature review on this work done by various research studies in energy efficient clustering and sleep-wake strategies in cognitive radio network is presented in this chapter.

Chapter 3 : Proposed work: In this proposed work, the proposed algorithm of clustering in CRN using sleep-wakeup strategy has done. It uses AP method, K-mean and sleep and wakeup strategy for making efficient clustering in CRN in which sleeping node is removed from CR network, select centroid from active node and then construct efficient cluster.

Chapter 4 : Simulation and results: In this section, simulation and desired result are done. It contains simulation of proposed algorithm based on clustering in cognitive radio network using sleep wake strategy on each node to make cluster efficient.

Chapter 5 : Conclusion and future work: In this last chapter, conclusion of all the research work and further research scope are discussed.

Chapter 2

Literature review

This section addresses the issues and research done till date in the field of clustering in the Cognitive radio system. The work by various analysts or scientists is briefly reviewed and discussed. In the previous years various strategies have been developed and presented in order to carry out clustering in cognitive radio network. Large part of this section covers the research done in field of clustering cognitive radio network.

Cognitive radio network being of wireless and intelligent in nature that adapt transmitter parameter through its environment automatically can make cluster using its radio nodes. Following examined are the researches which are utilized as the referenced inquires for this dissertation work.

2.1 Efficient clustering Algorithms in CRN's

In [7]. presented a “cluster-based MAC” convention known for KoN-MAC for Cognitive radio WSNs. this approach relies on a clustering plan for Wireless sensor network by Lin and Gerla [8]. Pritom et al. [9] gave a MAC protocol for “cluster-based CR-WSNs”, yet its MAC conspire depends on the “Low-Energy Adaptive clustering hierarchy” convention, that is uniquely intended for WSNs.

An epic clustering based detecting (CBSD) in cognitive radio WSNs was brought by Qu et al. [12]. In the strategy, sensor hubs are clustered into various sets dependent on their likeness in detecting outcomes. A target work is presented to recognize the ideal cluster number. Subtleties for creation of clusters and CH choice were not provided, and the performance was not contrasted and extent calculations or approaches.

Rauniyar and Shin [13] presented a clustering plan for collective range detecting relies on other algorithms [14] [15]. In the plan, a couple of nodes in a cluster can switch back and forth

between wake and sleep modes amid the detecting procedure.

An “spectrum aware cluster based” vitality efficient multimedia directing convention was presented by Shah et al. [7]. In this convention, SU hubs form a group with a excessive number of commonly accessible inert channels. The Cluster heads are chosen dependent on energy and “relative spectrum awareness”, with the end goal that non contiguous accessible spectrum bands are bunched and scheduled to give continuous transmission opportunity.

Salim et al. [16] presented clustering with brief support hubs. This plan has a xed cluster development span. It accept that CMs alter conveyance control dependent on distance to the CH.

Mustapa et al. [17] presented a vitality efficient spectrum aware fortification “learning based clustering” calculation for cognitive radio WSNs. In this approach, a part hub learns the energy detecting value for adjacent clusters so as to accomplish an ideal solution.

Maknoor and Sahid [18] presented a clustering plan called BECHR for cognitive radio WSNs. This plan choose a CH dependent on remaining vitality in an repetitive way. It works like traditional WSN clustering approach however with certain varieties.

Eletreeby et al. presented a “spectrum aware clustering” convention for cognitive radio WSNs called CogLEACH [8]. It is an expansion of the LEACH convention and utilizes the number of empty channels as a weight in the probability for every hub to turn into a CH. This work assesses CogLEACH in three distinctive models. It expands the throughput and lifetime of the system, contrasted with the normal LEACH convention that operates in similar settings.

Zhang et al. [19] and Han et al. [20] presented a “distributed spectrum aware clustering” for cognitive radio WSNs dependent on group wise obliged agglomerated grouping [21]. The primary idea is to set every hub as a dissever cluster toward the start and to combine the two closest clusters throughout every cycle until the group number is decreased to the ideal number. Amid each repetition, the inter-cluster separations are recomputation. At first, DSAC thinks about every hub as a CH, and then merges CHs inside every cycle until the number of CHs achieves the ideal number.

Ozger and Akan [22] and Ozger et al. [15] presented “event driven spectrum aware clustering” conventions which creates temporary clusters for every occasion in cognitive radio WSNs. These conventions decide qualified hubs for clustering on the basis of the nearby location of hubs between the occasion and the sink. CHs are chosen from among the candidate center

points subject to hub degree, channel openness, and detachment to the sink. Since this is event driven bunching, the groups are immediately ousted consequent to nishing data transmission. Thus, it isn't suitable for various circumstances.

Shahh and Aken [23] presented a "spectrum aware cluster based" directing (SCD) convention for cognitive radio WSNs. Nodes are grouped depending on their relative range mindfulness and remaining vitality. The protocol chooses CHs dependent on vitality and relative spectrum awareness, with the end goal that non-coterminous available spectrum bands are bunched and scheduled to give nonstop transmission oppurtunities.

Pei et al. [24] presented adaptive clustering for cognitive radio WSNs called low-vitality versatile uneven clustering chain of command (LEAUCH) for cognitive radio sensor systems. LEAUCH chooses applicant CH nodes dependent on the number of inert channels and chooses a CH dependent on separation from the sink. Top void the energy hole among CHs, it utilizes an uneven-sized clustering strategy.

Park et al. [25] presented a cognitive radio-based information type bunching (CR-HDC) algorithm for cognitive radio. It utilizes blocking and constrained end probabilities for CH transmission range and channel inhabitance.

Table 2.1: Comparison of already existing clustering plans for cognitive radio WSNs.

approches of clustering	Aims	Metrics	Execution Improvement	CHySelection	Unique Node
KoN-MAK	MAC protocol	Close to WSNs	Added channel load	Elected	Gateway node
CTSS	Energy effective Cooperative duty	Similarity between remote hubs	Energy utilization	No CH, but choses a node forispectrum sensing	NA
ECS	Cooperative spectrum sensing	Spectrum-aware node-grouping	Energy consumption (compared with DEEC algorithm for WSNs)	Predecided chance Only nodes in-nawake mode busy in the cluster-head chosen way	NA
SKEEM	Cross-layer routingo-protocol	maximum spectrum rank	clusters of optimal number	Depend on maximum spectrum energyorank	NA
CENTRE	Effective energy	Distance tothe CH	Grouping over-head(compared withDSAC)	Self declared	Temporary support (TS)cnode
EASA-RLC	Energy efficient PUn-detection	Optimal amount ofvclusters	Cooperative chance of detection	Amount of empty channels (similar to HEED)	NA
BECHR	Ranging detection	NA	Energy consumption (compared with LEACH)	Looping (depend on energy level)	No, but every hubs have GPS
Cog-LEAC-calculation in three different close replica	Amount of empty channels	Extension of LEACH	Amount of empty channels as a weight in the chance of every hubs	becoming an CH	NA

Clustering Plans	Aims	Metrics	Execution Improvement	CHSelection	Unique Node
EEC	Efficient energy	Ideal amount of clusters	NA	Remaining energy and amount of neighbour hubs	NA
ESEC/ mESEC	Event-driven grouping	Ranging availabilities	Energy consumption (with a late cost)	degree of a node, accessible channels, distance to the destination	NA
LEAUCH	Efficient energy	Number of channels available Uneven-sized clustering	Energy consumption System load balance	Amount of optimal channels Distance from the destination	NA
Virtual grouping	Control channel establishment MAC procedure	Similarities of spectrum opportunities Geographic location	Collision mitigation Control packet delay rate success	NA	NA
SCR	Routing	Spectrum measurements remaining energy	Delay Energy utilization mean packet	Rank energy spectrum	NA
CR-HDC	Efficient energy	Ideal transmission range for Geographical location	NA	Iterative (based on the remaining energy and average 1-hop distance to every other hubs)	NA

Chapter 3

Proposed Work

Here in this segment first the Affinity propagation method, K-means clustering, and sleep-wake strategy are discussed briefly and afterward both clustering algorithms are combined to make an efficient clustering in CRN. The proposed algorithm is well suited for finding or measuring the nodes number and clusters number etc. All radio node sends its information to the cluster head or pair of radio nodes for exchanging its information.

3.1 Preliminaries

Affinity propagation(AP) is a technique of cluster which is used for finding a good partition of huge data sets and exemplars(cluster head). The cluster head is a point that shows a similar characteristics to the data points in its neighborhood. This algorithm takes a set of pair-wise similarities as an input between exemplar(cluster head) and data points and identifies partitions iteratively which maximize the addition of similarities between exemplars and data points plus the addition of exemplar preferences. Here it assume exemplars as a cluster head and data points as radio nodes. In the affinity propagation algorithm simultaneously assuming in the data sets all the nodes potential cluster-head and send soft data to all data points(pairs of points) in the data sets iteratively until get an eligible set of exemplars. Availability and responsibility are the two soft data exchanged between data nodes.

Responsibility is the messages sent from data point to the exemplar and then it gets to reflect that how this exemplar is well suited for that data point. Responsibility $r(u, v)$ means messages are sent from u point to the v candidate exemplar this shows that v is well suited as an exemplar to the data point u .

$$r(u, v) = s(u, v) - \max_{v' \neq v} \{a(u, v) + s(u, v')\} \quad (3.1.1)$$

where,

- u is the data point;
- v is the exemplar or cluster head;
- v' represents other node except cluster head;
- $s(u, v)$ represents similarities between data point u and cluster head v ;
- $r(u, v)$ represents responsibility between data point u and cluster head v
- $a(u, v)$ represents the availability between data point u and cluster head v .

Availability is the message sent from candidate exemplar to the data point which show that it is well suited as a cluster head to that data point. Availability $a(u, v)$ means message is sent from v exemplar to the u point this shows that cluster head v is well suited for data node u . At each iteration, the availability and responsibility are updated using the following formula:

$$a(u, v) = \min\{0, r(v, v) + \sum_{u' \notin (u, v)} \max(0, r(u', v))\} \quad (3.1.2)$$

Here, $s(u, v)$ are the similarity between data node u and v . The similarity $s(u, v)$ simply denotes that how cluster head v is well suited for data point u . Similarity $s(u, v)$ is selected is depend on the requirements of the application and cluster.

For selecting the cluster-head, the number of selected clusters is influenced by preference value. If the preference value is small then the clusters number is small and when the preference data is large then the clusters number generation is more. Wireless network, the number of cluster formation is smaller using node degree while selecting the cluster head. So in the affinity propagation based clustering of cognitive radio networks, the degree of node u is a suitable for the preference value $p(u)$.

$$p(u) = s(u, u) = \alpha_u - \max_{u \in \mathcal{N}_i} \alpha_u \quad (3.1.3)$$

where,

- $p(u)$ represents the preference value of u ;
- α_u is the degree of nodes at data point u ;

- u' represents other node except data point u ;

The equation indicates subtraction of the maximum degree value of the neighboring node of node u from node degree(α_u) and in this way, preference value is achieved. It has to be ensured that the neighboring node degree should not be more than node u .

At the starting, availability is set to zero and both availabilities and responsibilities are iteratively updated using both the above formulae. The AP algorithm stop maybe after a certain number of the iterations, after if the exemplar or cluster head is constant for the number of iterations. Availability and responsibility can be combined and make an accumulated proof to find cluster head at any point during affinity propagation. If u is a cluster head then equation 3.1.3 must satisfy. To Identify the number of cluster head by affinity propagation algorithm which is affected by the value of the input of $s(u, u)$ self similarities of data nodes. Here self-similarity also called preferences, which shows how much well-suited cluster head is for the data node. High preferences show the good cluster head. The condition of a node u for becoming cluster head if equation 3.1.3 is satisfied.

$$a(u, u) + r(u, u) > 0 \quad (3.1.4)$$

where,

- $a(u, u)$ is availability at u ;
- α_u is the node degree at dtat point u ;
- u' represents other node except data point u ;

3.1.1 Selection of cluster head

The node u exchanges the data and find out the availability $a(u, v)$ and responsibility $r(u, v)$ values for every neighbor node $v \in \mathcal{N}$, where N is the total number of neighbor nodes. For becoming a potential cluster head, it is checked whether the node u is eligible or not by using the equation 3.1.3. If an neighboring node satisfies this then that neighboring node is an potential cluster head otherwise node u behave as a member node. After node u become a potential cluster head, it again compares the highest number of degree level with other potential cluster

head. If node u contains the highest number of degree level then it becomes a cluster head otherwise node u behave as a member node. The steps of selecting cluster head is given below in the figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Baddour's AP approach steps at node u .

3.1.2 Finding Euclidean distance

Euclidean distance is used in K Means calculations. In view of Euclidean distance, every perception is assigned out to one of the clusters in light of least distance. In K-mean clustering algorithm, Euclidean distance is calculated between two nodes given in below equation.

$$Euclidean\ distance = \sqrt{(u_1 - v_1)^2 + (u_2 - v_2)^2} \quad (3.1.5)$$

Where, u_1, u_2 and v_1, v_2 are the coordinate of the node's location.

3.2 Sleep-wake mode strategies

Sleep-wake strategy is the process of a node to get into sleep and wake mode. A node gets into sleep mode or wake mode if the condition is passed [7]. The following figure 3.1 shows AP procedure to make cluster head.

3.2.1 Applying Battery state based sleep-wake strategy

In this sleep-wake strategy, the wireless node goes to sleep mode if the battery capacity is less than the threshold battery capacity. For attaining a node to be an active then battery capacity must be greater than its threshold [7] [10].

Blow represents threshold battery state when a node goes from active mode to sleep mode, B_{hi} represents the threshold battery capacity when nodes go from sleep mode to active mode [11].

$$P_{s \rightarrow a}(c, q, b, r) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } b/B \geq b_{hi} \\ 0, & \text{if } b/B < b_{hi} \end{cases}$$

and

$$P_{a \rightarrow s}(c, q, b, r) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } b/B > b_{low} \\ 1, & \text{if } b/B < b_{low} \end{cases}$$

where,

- b is an battery state;
- B represents capacity of Battery ;
- b_{hi} is threshold battery capacity when sensor node switches from active to sleep mode;
- b_{low} is threshold battery capacity when sensor node switches from sleep to active mode;
- c, q, b and r are channel state, number of packets in the queue, battery state and solar radiation state repectively.

$B_{low} > 0$ indicate that the battery capacity never going to down. Here it assumes the value of blow is 0.05 and b_{hi} is 0.3 where a node goes to sleep. if battery state is less than 0.05 times total battery capacity and it again on wakeup state when battery state is more than or equal to 0.3 times the total battery capacity.

Average battery capacity is calculated in the following:

$$\bar{b} = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B (\sum_{a,c,r,s,x,m} \pi(a, c, r, s, x)) \quad (3.2.1)$$

where,

- $\bar{b}$ is the average battery capacity;
- a represents state of batch Markovian arrival process;
- π represents the probability matrix;
- m is mode of the node.

Battery average capacity is proportional to the battery size(i.e., $0 \leq \bar{b} \leq 1$)

The probability of sleep and wake-up method for packet blocking are as follows:

$$P_{sleep} = \sum_{a,c,r,x} \pi(x, a, c, b, r, m) \text{ if } m = \text{sleep or } b = 0 \quad (3.2.2)$$

If any node goes to sleep mode then this node can not receive any incoming packets. So the coming packets are not allowed. The probability of packet blocking is $P_{block} = P_{sleep}$

3.3 Proposed Algorithm

The main aim of our proposed algorithm is to create an efficient cluster. In this first, it chooses the cluster head by using Affinity propagation algorithm. Here cluster head is chosen by calculating the preference of the node. To calculate preference $p(u)$ of node u , the maximum degree of a neighboring node is subtracted from the degree of node u given in the equation 3.1.3.

By doing this it gets the cluster head. Now applying this cluster head to the k-mean clustering algorithm to make an efficient cluster.

3.3.1 Algorithm

In proposed flow diagram, it starts with the total number of radio nodes in the network. In that network, sleep and wake-up strategies are applied to check whether a certain node is in the active(wake-up) mode or in the sleep mode. Here it is assured that the capacity of the battery node should be greater than or equal to threshold value. After selecting a number of active radio nodes, Cluster head or centroid are chosen by using affinity propagation method. Now in the next step find out the node distance from the centroid using Euclidean distance formula. The flow diagram of proposed algorithm is shown in figure 3.2.

Further here it checks if two nodes having its distances are equal then at that situation nodes is selected which is having a higher degree otherwise minimum distance is selected for the cluster. Iterate these steps until achieved the same centroid value.

The Pseudo Algorithm for clustering in CRN is given illustrated in Algorithm 1.

Figure 3.2: Flow diagram of proposed algorithm

Algorithm 1: Light Source Authentication in ADAS/Autonomous Vehicles

Input: e, n, A_{UID}

Output: Transmit EncryptedID;

Calculate the C_{UID} and insert in FLS

for i in all nodes **do**

if $b_nodes[i] > b_thres.$ **then**
 $A[j++] = i;$
 end

end

Select cluster head by AP from $A_{node}[]$ and put each clusters[]

$NonCluster[] = nodes[] - clusters[];$

for i in all $NonCluster$ **do**

$min = maximumValue;$
 $selectCluster = NULL;$
 for j in all clusters **do**
 if $midDist(i, j) < min$ **then**
 $min = midDist(i, j);$
 $selectCluster = j;$
 else if $midDist(i, j) = min$ and $degree(j) > degree(selectNode)$ **then**
 $selectCluster = j;$
 end
 put $nonCluster[j]$ in $clusters[selectCluster];$

end

return cluster[];

The above-proposed algorithm is explained the steps:

- a) **Step 1:** In this proposed algorithm, first, choose only the node which is in wakeup mode. Take the waking node as an input, a list of node z and it takes centroid or cluster head L from AP method for which is it has to find out the value of preference of each node to get centroid.
- b) **Step 2:** Now it find out the Euclidean distance of a node to each centroid and select the

centroid which is having a minimum distance from the node and put that node in the cluster by using euclidean distance shown in the the equation 3.3.1.

$$\text{Euclidean distance} = \sqrt{(u_1 - v_1)^2 + (u_2 - v_2)^2} \quad (3.3.1)$$

Where (u_1, u_2) and (v_1, v_2) are coordinate location of the node.

If two nodes are having same Euclidean distance then it compares the number of degree of both the nodes. The node is selected which is having the maximum number of node degree. Otherwise, assign a node to the cluster which is having minimum distance with the centroid.

$$\text{Node degree} = \text{No. of the associated node} \quad (3.3.2)$$

- c) **Step 3:** For the cluster movement step, the cluster head position is upgraded by moving cluster head to the mean of the nodes position assign to that cluster.

$$\mu^v = \frac{1}{|c_v|} \sum_{u \in c_v} x(u), v \in [1, k] \quad (3.3.3)$$

where $|c_v|$ = number of nearest nodes allocated to cluster head v , and μ^v is the different centroid and $x(u)$ is the location of the nearest node.

Chapter 4

Simulation and Results

In this segment, the analyze the performance of the algorithm which is proposed and evaluated with the assistance of computer simulations. The strength and effectiveness of the present work is analyzed utilizing the simulations using MATLAB. This proposed clustering based model is compared with other three similar existing clustering model, namely, Cogmesh [5], SOC approach [12] and cluster based approach [13]. The simulation area is 10 km^2 , where the cognitive nodes are situated arbitrarily in the recreation environment. 10 available channels and 500 meters communication range for every node are assumed.

Figure 4.1: Number of cluster against number of node

It is shown in the figure 4.1. that increase in the number of node also lead to increase in the number of clusters for all the three approaches along with the proposed model.

In our proposed approach, 14 clusters are made in the network of 50 nodes while 13, 12

and 10 clusters are made in the same network for SOC approach, cluster based approach and CogMesh respectively. In the network of 150 nodes, 16 clusters are constructed by proposed approach while 17, 18 and 32 clusters are constructed by CogMesh approach, cluster based approach and Soc approach respectively. On the other hand when the node is 300 in the network then 19 number of clusters are constructed by proposed approach while 24, 27 and 42 number of clusters are constructed by Cluster based approach, CogMesh and SOC approach respectively. It is seen that in SOC approach, as the number of node is increasing, the number of cluster are also increasing highly compared to the other three approach along with proposed algorithm. It is seen that less number of cluster are constructed by proposed approach while comparing with other three approaches. Thus, this proposed model approach is efficient clustering method for cognitive radio network.

Figure 4.2: Simulation graph of Energy of whole network vs time

Next, energy consumption for the whole network is studied. Explicit states of the simulation are as per the following: 80 nodes are arbitrarily dissipated in a $(150 \times 150)^2$ meter region; Communication radius of the initial node is 30m and beginning energy held is 100; node energy utilization in the working state is 1.5 every second and in resting or sleeping state is 0.2 every second. The energy of the node edge set at 75. At the point when a node's energy is under 50, it might be viewed as that it has failed and couldn't work, so it never again associated with the working node decision. The relationship between energy utilization and identifying radius is in

the following equation 4.0.1.

$$E = Cr_s \quad (4.0.1)$$

- E is the energy utilization;
- C is the energy utilization conversion factor;
- r_s is the node detection radius.

The threshold energy setting is prompted the number of excess nodes to lessen in the last area, yet in the state of the whole system, it makes the circulation of intensity increasingly normal and adjusted and improves the feasibility of the system. Systems by and large energy utilization simulation appeared in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.3: Energy of a node(First node is working and then sleeping)

Bends in the diagram showed the general energy utilization of the system under the condition that there has energy edge set and has not individually, where the intersection purpose of two broken lines demonstrated that the system without setting energy limit has developed energy "empty" at the very point on the grounds that the working nodes energy has been depleted, and it can not keep on working. The figure additionally demonstrates that despite the fact that the number of working nodes increment, the sleeping component with energy limit expanded the life of whole remote sensor systems.

Figure 4.4: Energy of a node(First node is sleeping and then working)

Its entire lifetime can be separated into two sorts of states: working and resting or sleeping. Subsequent to setting the energy edge for a single node, simulation examination of these two states as appeared in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4.

Bends in the above figure indicate the same significance as those in Fig.4.2. From the figure it can be seen that regardless of nodes begin at which sort of states, (working or sleeping), subsequent to setting the energy edge, the system re-judge nodes to work or to sleep at the certain time, making the node lifetime has been incredibly improved contrasted and the nodes continually being at work. In this way setting the threshold energy of a node can be well-balanced the energy utilization of nodes, and certification the trustworthiness of system inclusion progressively.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Future Work

This dissertation work contributes toward the efficient clustering in a cognitive radio wireless sensor network and the future directions are also pointed out which can be carried out in order to improve network performance.

5.1 Conclusions

In the proposed work, the k-mean and affinity propagation methods are used to make more efficient clustering. This strategy checks whether the node of a network is in sleep mode or in wake-up mode. Only those nodes in the network which are on wake-up mode are selected, and non-active nodes or sleeping nodes are removed from the network. The checking of active mode or sleep mode is done by checking the capacity of the battery of the node. If capacity is more than or equal to threshold value then that node is on active mode otherwise it is on sleep mode. Then the K-means clustering algorithm is used for making a cluster. In this, Euclidean distance is calculated between node and centroid. Simulation results show that proposed work creates a lesser number of clusters than other works when the number of nodes increases which reduces the overall overhead of the network.

The scope of future work can be considered in energy utilization in mobile cognitive radio network using a cluster-based algorithm to deduce the jamming in the network and for the lifetime of the cognitive radio network network.

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